

EXPERIMENTAL AND ECONOMIC STUDIES OF OPTIMUM MATRIX ACIDIZING IN VARIOUS SANDSTONE RESERVOIRS

Ali S. AlNetaifi

Petroleum and Natural Gas Engineering Department, College of Engineering, King Saud University, Riyadh, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

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Abstract: *Sandstone acidizing in oil industry has been considered a crucial process to treat and enhance permeability of hydrocarbon reservoirs due to permeability reduction using drilling mud. Corrosion rate is a significant parameter in a traditional acidizing which is used mineral acids to do sandstone treatment, and this parameter can be norm to apply treatment successfully. The main objective in this paper is to discover a new technique to apply the treatment job by injecting organic mud acids mixture as one-step in order to minimize the treatment cost and implementation time practically. Furthermore, this technique is injected inside the various scenarios such as fractured and unfractured “homogeneous” cores, damaged and undamaged cores using drilling mud, and the treatment job is then evaluated by the pre- and post- permeabilities measurements at high pressure and temperature. Moreover, the consumption and cost of acids and materials using the new treatment technique for each experiment are investigated, and then compare them with the traditional treatment technique economically. The porosities and permeabilities of unfractured “homogeneous” cores in both damaged and undamaged cases are concluded enhancement and improvement after complete treatment stages. In contrast, the permeability of 45 degree fractured core is mistreatment especially around fracture because it is observed that the acids can pass through the fracture and channel which do not have any resistances. Finally, a traditional treatment technique is costly rather than a new treatment technique economically, thus, the new treatment technique can be more benefit for industry. In order to treat and simulate homogenous formation, the consumption of acids in damaged core is logically higher than in undamaged core.*

1. Introduction

The main principle to apply acidizing and treatment jobs in the field is known that initiate

and establish channels around the wellbore, and treat the pores of reservoir from any damages that can happened from drilling mud.

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When those jobs are applied successfully, formation permeability is enhanced, and it is then led to well productivity improvement. There are several parameters that can be studied before treatment jobs can be implemented, and those refer to type of formation, damage type and the suitable acids that can react with formation minerals as well as formation fluid. The traditional mud acids mixture, which has been used to apply sandstone treatment, is composed of various percentages of hydrofluoric and hydrofluoric acids, and its percentage strongly depends on the mineralogy of formation. When the mixture is selected based on the mineralogy of hydrocarbon formation, it can react with the formation minerals such as clays and silica. As a result, all minerals can be successfully dissolved, and then initiate and create channels which lead to permeability and production enhancements. On the contrary, selection of mud acids mixture to implement treatment was not correctly, this can causes precipitations phenomena inside the formation which led to damage formation, and its productivity reduction (Al-Dahlan et al., 2001; Thomas et al., 2001).

It was supposed that the energy demand will be increased up to forty percentages, thus, the

enhancement of oil and gas productivity have been very significant in the worldwide (Aboud et al., 2007). The intelligent method to elect the acids mixture has been obtained to create a crucial technique for acidizing job at high pressure as well as temperature. Since the traditional method to apply acidizing job caused fast reaction with formation minerals, and then it led to insufficient treatment (Al-Harbi et al., 2013). Several researches have been studied to find new mud acids mixture in order to minimize the issues where occur in fields. It was studied the efficient of sandstone acidizing using organic mud acids mixture (Al-Harthy et al., 2008; Yang et al., 2012). Some practical studies were done to stimulate and treat water supply wells by injecting acids mixture which is composed of 5wt% acetic acid and 5wt% hydrochloric acid (Hashem et al., 1999; Nasr-El-Din et al., 1997). In addition, formic acids can be used in the well stimulation at concentration up to 9 wt%. The principle to mix organic acids with hydrochloric acid in acidizing job can be generally in the form of iron control agents, and corrosion inhibitors.

The aim of this paper is experimentally investigated the intelligent technique to implement matrix acidizing inside sandstone

reservoirs using organic mud acids mixture which is composed of 2wt% hydrofluoric acid and 15wt% acetic acid. Furthermore, this technique is applied on several scenarios at high pressure and temperature which are corresponding 1000 psi and 140°F. To create more sustainable in economy as well as energy, all stages in new treatment technique are then studied to find the costs and prices of stimulation processes, and compare them with all stages in the traditional treatment economically.

2. Literature Review

The well stimulation has been an important technique to treat and enhance production from hydrocarbon formation. When its processes are not costly, the hydrocarbon can sell cheap, and the sustainability can be then achieved in the current era. Matrix acidizing and hydraulic fracturing have been known most common techniques in well stimulation in industry. Furthermore, matrix acidizing technique has been possibly developed because this technique is considered the chemical reactions between used acids and the formation minerals, and the results of its reactions cannot create any issues in the fields. The major principle for chemical reactions between acids and formation minerals

dissolves and removes any damages in hydrocarbon formation, hence, the permeability improvement, and this leads to increase hydrocarbon production (Crowe et al., 1992). In addition, this technique can be used in fractured reservoir and high permeability formation with damages. Appropriate acids with formation fluid and mineralogy, acid concentration and acid injection have been major factors in treatment and acidizing jobs. It was observed that acidizing of low permeability sandstone formation is more efficient rather than high permeability sandstone formation (McCune et al., 1975). In the other side, the acidizing of high porosity formation is less efficient rather than low porosity formation.

Generally, the aspect to inject hydrofluoric acid inside sandstone formation is to acidize and dissolve the damages which cause from using drilling mud, and these can be definitely kind of clay. Basically, pre-flush stage was used for removing mud cake filter and damages around wellbore. It is well known that sandstone formation contains quartz and clay, and the hydrofluoric acid can react with clay very fast comparing with quartz., It was studied the reaction between pure hydrofluoric acid and sandstone formation, and it was concluded

that the hydrofluoric acid naturally reacts with sandstone formation, in the contrast, the sulphuric and hydrochloric acids cannot have any reactions with sandstone formation (Smith and Hendrickson, 1965).

The structure of clay and its type were been significant to select the properly acids, and the results of their reactions (Gidley, 2000). It was concluded that there are several reaction stages that can result from the reaction between hydrofluoric acid and kaolinite, and these are called primary, secondary and tertiary reaction stages. Reaction between hydrofluoric and kaolinite chemically results high concentration of fluorosilicic. In addition, this acid can react with kaolinite as secondary stage. The result from the secondary reaction stage is silicate and aluminium fluoride which can increase the possibility of precipitations inside the formation, hence, they can lead to damage formation. The tertiary reaction stage can be occurred when hydrofluoric acid chemically reacts with kaolinite inside formation. It is indicated that the tertiary reaction stage chemically result other complicated minerals, and they can cause damage in formation. Researcher confirmed that reaction rate of the secondary and tertiary stages increase with temperature increase (Gdanski, 1998 and

2000). In addition, it was investigated that the secondary reaction rate between clay and hydrofluoric acid is very slow when the injection temperature is less than 125 °F. In the other hand, reaction acceleration between aluminium fluoride and kaolinite can be high when injection temperature is higher than 200 °F.

It was studied that the reaction stages between formation and mineral mud acids mixture, which is composed of the hydrochloric and hydrofluoric acids (Al-Harbi et al., 2013). The reaction was categorized to three groups where strongly depend on the distance from the injection face. It was observed that the reaction, where is near the wellbore, is called the primary reaction, and its results contain silica fluoride as well as aluminium fluoride. In addition, it was detected that this kind of reaction stages definitely dissolves clay and quartz minerals without any precipitations. Once mineral mud acid goes away from the injection face, the reaction of primary products can be occurred, and this stage of reaction is called the secondary reaction. Furthermore, the silica gel in the secondary stage can precipitate with slow reaction rate. When the products from the secondary reaction flow more distance rather than secondary stage,

precipitations of silica gel can be happened, and this is called the tertiary reaction. Obviously, the acidizing job of sandstone formation cannot success and treat in order to increase the possibility of secondary and tertiary reactions under reservoir conditions which can be high temperature and pressure. According to previous observations about reactions, the main target to add hydrochloric acid to mineral mud acid is for decreasing the concentration of hydrofluoric acid, which can reduce the products precipitations, and it is for keeping acidic environment.

The products, which result from reaction between acid and formation minerals, can precipitate in formation in order to minimize the porosity and permeability of formation (Mahmoud et al., 2011). The precipitations types in sandstone formation by acidizing job were explained (Smith and Hendrickson, 1965). They can be namely calcium fluoride precipitations, potassium and sodium precipitations, and hydrated silica precipitations. The first kind of precipitations can cause in order to react between fluosilicic acid and potassium and sodium ions. The second precipitations can be created by reacting between fluorideion and calcium ion, and the solubility of these precipitations is

relatively low, and it can be eliminated by injecting adequate pre-flush job such as hydrochloric acid. The last precipitations, which are namely colloidal silica, are extremely complex comparing with other precipitations. In order to increase the reaction rate between acids and formation minerals, the pressure and temperature factors were observed crucial factors in matrix acidizing of sandstone reservoirs (Farley et al., 1970). Two issues, which can be happened using mineral mud acids mixture, were high corrosion rate as well as the precipitations, thus, treatment cannot success and this led to damage formation (Thomas et al., 2002). Based on previous reasons, researchers decided to explore and discover new mud acids mixture which can be used instead of mineral mud acids mixture, they used organic mud acids mixture to implement acidizing job (Yang et al., 2012). This was composed of organic acid and hydrofluoric acid, and it can solve several issues in the field conditions such as corrosion problems, precipitations and others. Applications of organic mud acids mixture have been massive utilized in the field conditions in order to provide high efficiency results with low corrosion rate especially at high pressure and temperature. Furthermore,

once the hydrochloric acid is sensitive with clay an organic acid can be an appropriate and perfect acid to use. Formic and acetic acids and a combination of hydrofluoric acid with organic acid were considered the most common acids used in the field, and this mixture was called an organic mud acids.

Reaction rate and the precipitations strongly depend on the formation and fluid properties and reservoir condition. When the porous media contains sodium and potassium ions, those can react with hydrofluoric acid, and produce sodium fluorosilicate and potassium fluorosilicate. Consequently, pre-flush stage was required to avoid any precipitations inside formation using hydrochloric acid (McLeod, 1984) while the mixture of ammonium chloride and organic acid was used in pre-flush stage (Thomas et al., 2002). It was supposed to add organic acid in hydrochloric acid as a pre-flush stage, and authors concluded that mixture is more effective rather than hydrochloric acid injection alone (Shafiq and Shuker, 2013).

The main target of adding hydrochloric acid or organic acid in the mud or main acid was for preventing silica precipitations as hydrate colloid (Yang et al., 2012). Generally, the precipitations, which result from acidizing job,

can be avoided using several techniques. These techniques can absolutely relate to stages of acidizing procedures which are pre-flush, main treatment and post-flush stages. Basically, the pre-flush stage was for dissolving potassium, sodium and calcium ions since those ions can cause insoluble silicates when the silicates react with mud acid. In the main treatment stage, the main purpose of this stage was to dissolve quartz, clays and other minerals, furthermore, the carbonates can be removed in this stage. Finally, the goals of post-flush stage in the acidizing job were for retaining the wettability of sandstone formation as in the original stage, and cleaning and removing the spent acid from formation. The appropriate amount of acid injection inside sandstone formation as post-flush stage was required, and solvents, hydrochloric acid, ammonium chloride, or organic acid can be injected to clean and displace any minerals as well as spent acids (Aboud et al., 2007).

To decrease the corrosion rate as well as incompatibility in acidizing job, surfactants and corrosion inhibitor can be used, and those additives cannot alter any things in the stimulation process (Rabie and Nasr-El-Din, 2015). Surfactants can solve any issues that relate to incompatibility, it can be added and

used in main treatment acid and post-flush stages. On the other hand, to protect and keep the integrity of the metal, corrosion inhibitors can be used during all acidizing job (McLeod, 1984).

It has been well known that formic, citric and acetic acids are organic acids, and they are called carboxylic acids, furthermore, all of them are known weak acids comparing with the hydrochloric or sulphuric acids. They can be naturally found from gas condensate wells, however, the acetic acid has been commonly injected to retain acidity and eliminate any solids precipitations, and it has been significant implication especially for the integrity of metals such as vessels and pipes, this kind of organic acid has been also known environmentally friendly. The viscosity, density and molecular weight of acetic acid are 2 cp, 1.05 gm/cc and 60 respectively. Furthermore, Saudi formation water “SFW” is composed of 5.89wt% sodium chloride, 2.24wt% calcium chloride and 0.15wt% magnesium chloride, its density and viscosity values are 1.065 gm/cc and 1.3 cp respectively.

The acetic acid can react with aqueous solution, which is composed of sodium chloride, magnesium chloride and calcium chloride, and their results are hydrochloric

acid. Increase the concentration of acetic acid in mud acid with chloride ion existence at high temperature perhaps results the highest concentration of hydrochloric acid, and this leads to increase the corrosion rate. The calcium and magnesium can be separately ions, and they precipitate inside the porous media. Hence, ammonium chloride is candidate and used instead of hydrochloric acid since the ammonium chloride is mildly acidic and, the PH of 5wt% ammonium chloride solution can be 5.5, moreover, the aspect of ammonium chloride is a compatible solution with acidizing job. To sum up, it is injected 5wt% of ammonium chloride solution as pre-treatment stage, and main treatment acids mixture is a combination of 5wt% ammonium chloride and organic mud acid “15wt% HAc and 2wt% HF”. It is concluded that the amount of hydrochloric acid, which creates from chemical reactions of used fluids in all steps in each experiment at high pressure and temperature, is sufficient.

Based on previous descriptions, this paper is addressed the new mechanism of matrix treatment in both fractured and unfractured sandstone formations by injecting mud acids mixture as one step. It is studied the

comparison between the new treatment and

3. Laboratory Apparatus and Procedures

3.1. Equipment and Materials

Several Berea sandstone cores are conducted to do the acidizing job in this study. And those have been well known that they are composed of high percentage of quartz and low percentage of clay, consequently, the acidizing procedure can be more efficient rather than hydraulic fracturing since its permeabilities are actually moderate up to high. For fractured sandstone core, the electrical saw is used to create fracture or channel “2mm width and 2mm depth” upon the core with 45 degree angle to examine the treatment job in fractured sandstone formation. Balance, pycnometer, viscometer, vacuum desiccator, pump, accumulators, temperature tapes and controller, injection pump, confining pump, Hassler core holder and back pressure regulator are used to build up vacuum and flooding units, and rock and fluid properties are experimentally measured regarding to previous instruments. Graduated plastic tubes, containers and flasks are recommend to use in the acidizing stage to eliminate any adsorption effects with acids. Saudi formation water “SFW” is prepared to mimic Saudi reservoir, and it is composed of 5.89wt% sodium chloride, 2.24wt% calcium chloride and 0.15wt%

traditional treatment techniques economically. magnesium chloride. Drilling mud, which is composed of bentonite and its density 1.17 gm/cc, is prepared to inject inside core, and represent a real issue case. Solution of 5wt% ammonium chloride is prepared for implementing pre- and post-treatment stages. In addition, 15wt% acetic and 2wt% hydrofluoric acids are mixed with 5wt% ammonium chloride solution to apply main treatment stage

3.2 Experimental Procedures

The treatment experiments using organic mud acids mixture, which is composed of 15wt% acetic acid and 2wt% hydrofluoric acid, are conducted in this study. There are several phases or stages of measurements that have been done in this paper. In the first step measurement, unfractured and fractured Berea sandstone cores are dried and warmed for several hours using oven, the weights of all cores are balanced to find the dry weight for all cores. After that, all cores are put in a vacuum desiccator, and vacuum pump is then worked to evacuate air from the pores of all cores. When the vacuum gauge goes to the minimum value, the valve of flask, which is filled with Saudi formation water to simulate the real reservoir, is opened for one hour to make sure

all pores inside cores filled and saturated with SFW. After all cores saturation with SFW, each core is balanced to determine saturated weight, and apply this step to other cores. Pore volume of each core can be then computed by subtracting dry weight from saturated weight and then divide by the density of SFW, and the bulk volume of each core can be determined using cylindrical volume. Finally, porosity of each core, which its equation is defined as the pore volume is divided by bulk volume, can be calculated, and this porosity is called pre-porosity which is before the treatment process. Moreover, in the fractured sandstone core, it consists of two kinds of porosities which are namely primary and secondary porosities. The primary porosity can be found similar procedures of determining the unfractured sandstone core porosity as discussed before, on the other hand, the secondary porosity, which is the fracture capacity to retain fluid inside it, can be calculated by dimensions of fracture.

All experiments are performed using both unfractured and fractured Berea sandstone cores that are approximately 3.6 inches long and 1.5 inches diameter. The pore pressure and

temperature of all experiments are 1000 psi and 140°F respectively. To demonstrate its pressure and temperature conditions, the back pressure regulator and temperature tapes and controller are used, in addition, the confining pump is used to adjust the overburden pressure which its value is 1300 psi so that the pressure differences between the pore and overburden pressure are almost 300 psi. Using Teledyne ISCO Pump, the injection rate of SFW, main treatment, drainage and imbibition processes is 2 cc/min except the injection rate of pre-treatment and post-treatment stages using ammonium chloride solution is 5 cc/min due to clean porous media from magnesium, sodium and calcium precipitations, and the remaining organic mud acid. There are two pressure transducers, where are located in the inlet and outlet of the core holder, and the main purpose of them is to read the inlet pressure as well as the outlet pressure, and the pressure drop can be then calculated. All samples are collected using the plastic containers for treatment process. All materials and equipment, that have been in the coreflood experiments, are shown in the Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic of Coreflood Unit

In each experiment, the core is put inside Hassler core holder, and the previous conditions are applied on it, and those conditions should be consistent in all experiments. Saudi formation water is injected inside the sandstone core to find the absolute permeability of the core regarding to Darcy's Law. The ammonium chloride solution is then injected to try removing any chemical elements such as sodium, calcium and magnesium that can cause any precipitations that lead to

formation damage. When the pressure drop or difference is constant, the permeability can be calculated, and this permeability is called pre-treatment permeability. To be more realistic, the damage can be created by injecting one pore volume of drilling mud inside core, the permeability can be found, and this is called damaged permeability, and its value is generally very low comparing with other permeabilities. After that, the main treatment is applied by injecting the organic mud acids

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mixture till the pressure drop is constant or no more change, and this is called treated permeability. The ammonium chloride solution is then injected at 5 cc/min to remove the remaining organic mud acids mixture from the porous media, and the post-treatment permeability is then determined. At the final procedure of the treatment process, all cores are cleaned, dried and saturated with SFW to find its dry and saturated weights to calculate their porosities that are called post-porosities.

4. Results and Discussion

Three experiments have been employed to investigate sandstone treatment from different angles and views, and these can be treatment technique, homogeneity of porous media and

the treatment of damaged core. All Porosities of pre- and post- treatments for both fractured and unfractured “homogeneous” cores are obtained as listed in the **Error! Reference source not found.** All values in **Error! Reference source not found.** are reasonable and logical values, and Core (A) and Core (B) have almost porosity enhancements with 113% and 121% respectively. On the other hand, the total porosity after Core (C) treatment does not computed due to several reasons that will be mentioned later with more details. However, it has higher porosity value rather than other cores, since it has fracture or channel with 45 degree angle approximately.

Table 1: Properties of Berea Sandstone Cores: Pre- and Post- Treatments.

Core	V _{Bulk} , cc	Phi _{sec.} %	Total Phi Pre_Tre,%	Total Phi Post_Tre,%
A	104.83	0	19.31	21.74
B	104.83	0	18.20	22.0
C	104.83	1.90	19.73	Mistreatment

As explained before, all results are got at similar conditions which mean that the back pressure regulator, temperature and injection rate of all experiments are set same values. During experiment run, the inlet and outlet pressures are recorded to compute permeability regarding to Darcy’s Law. Several permeabilities values have been calculated in this study, and these

values exactly relate to the viscosity of fluid where flows inside the porous media. The permeabilities of Saudi formation water, ammonium chloride and drilling mud injections inside Core (A) have been experimentally measured and computed, its values are 80 mD, 108 mD and 28 mD respectively. The target to inject of five pore volumes of 5wt% ammonium

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chloride solution after SFW is to prevent any precipitations that can be occurred in the main treatment, and this comment agrees with mentioned observation (Yang et al., 2012). For Core (C), its SWF, NH_4Cl and drilling mud permeabilities are 176 mD, 235 mD and 55 mD respectively, and these values clear that the increase in permeability in Core (C) is due to channel and fracture that are on it. Core (B) does not have damage scenario, consequently, the permeabilities of SFW and ammonium chloride solution are 87 mD and 118 mD. As mentioned in the experimental procedures section, the ammonium chloride solution can be achievable when it is injected at high rate, since its property is slightly and mildly acidic, and it can be the best option to use in treatment process to decrease the corrosion rate instead of hydrochloric acid. As described in literature review, the ammonium chloride and water can be chemically reaction, and its reaction results hydrochloric acid. To sum up, fractured sandstone has highest permeability rather than other cores which are damaged and undamaged cores. Furthermore, permeabilities of unfractured sandstone cores are almost similar. The main and post-treatment stages using organic mud acids mixture and ammonium chloride solution are applied on three

mentioned cores. As petroleum engineers, the target of stimulation process especially on acidizing process returns the permeability to either the original permeability “100%” or permeability enhancement “more than 100%”. As indicted in a main treatment stage in Figure 2, the trend of the main treatment stage slightly decreases until it reaches to 88%, this occurs because the organic mud acids mixture reacts with quartz and clays, the reaction products can therefore precipitate and plug some channels where are located inside the porous media. Consequently, there is no permeability enhancement especially on core which has not any damages, and this observation agrees with the published results. Post-treatment stage using ammonium chloride solution is then injected at high flow rate to clean the porous media from any precipitations and remove remaining amount of acids to eliminate any additional reactions that can lead to damage the core or formation.

In the post-treatment stage, the trend seems that the injection of 2.5 pore volumes of ammonium chloride solution is sufficient to provide the highest percentage of permeability improvement “136 %” for undamaged sandstone cores.

In Figure 3, it is cleared that organic mud acids mixture, which is called a main treatment stage, can be successful method to improve permeability from 28 mD to 99 mD which represent 25% to 92% from the original permeability value. This change is due to the successful reaction between hydrofluoric acid and clays which are fast reaction, and acetic acid and ammonium chloride can be accelerate and regulate the solubility process inside the core at high pressure and temperature. On the

other side, the improvement of permeability is obviously rapid once the ammonium chloride solution is injected, and the permeability enhances from 92% to 136% approximately. This enhancement can be resulted from the removing all reaction products that be precipitated from the main treatment stage since the injection of this fluid is under high injection rate comparing with others injection stages.

Figure 2: Permeability Profile of Unfractured Berea Sandstone Core without Damaging during Main and post Stages at 1000 Psi and 140 oF. “Core (B)”

In both Figure 2 and Figure 3, the percentages of permeability enhance for both cores, which have damaged and undamaged scenarios, are almost similar, and their percentages values are around 136%.

It is obvious to notice that the treatment behaviour in fractured core is completely different than the treatment of unfractured sandstone formations. The Figure 4 is shown the treatment behaviour inside the fractured sandstone core, and the percentage of permeability improvement is almost decreased

from 25% to 15% at the beginning of organic mud acids mixture injection. This is referred to increase possibility of plugging fracture regarding to use the drilling mud, in addition, the fines could be immigrated through the high permeable fracture. The improvement in permeability especially on main treatment stage is slowly occurred as indicated in the trend in Figure 4, and its increment is from 15% till 42% at five pore volumes of organic mud acid injection.

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Figure 3: Permeability Profile of Unfractured Berea Sandstone Core with Damaging using Drilling Mud during Main and Post-Treatment Stages at 1000 Psi and 140 oF. “Core (A)”

Figure 4: Permeability Profile of Fractured Berea Sandstone Core with Damaging using Drilling Mud during Main and Post Treatment Stages at 1000 Psi and 140 oF. “Core (C)”

In the post-treatment stage, the permeability percentage is however increased from the 42% till 68%, hence, the enhancement of permeability in fractured sandstone core has not been achievable and successful. Because it has not returned to the original permeability, and this result is logical and it can agree with

published observation (McCune et al., 1975). In the fractured sandstone core, the major phenomena is visually detected that the damaged permeability cannot be treated and stimulated in both main treatment and post treatment stages, since organic mud acids mixture and ammonium chloride solution

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bypass the damaged area where is located around fracture on the sandstone core. Thus, the treatment in fractured sandstone core using organic mud acids mixture cannot be successful as shown in the Figure 5.

5. Economic Section

Economy side has been a very significant parameter to assess either treatment or acidizing job practically, and this factor relates to treatment stages, used acids for doing treatment, suitable tools and metals with used acids under reservoir conditions. Based on the prices of all materials to calculate the cost of each treatment stage, that have been implemented, ammonium chloride solution, hydrochloric acid, acetic acid and hydrofluoric acid prices are 0.16\$/cc, 0.61\$/cc, 0.34\$/cc and 1.0\$/cc respectively, and it is assumed the tax value is 10 %. The general equation for calculating can be found through the equation below:

$$\text{Cost of Treatment Stages } \$/\text{PV} = \frac{\text{Cumulative fluid Injection} * (\sum \text{Price}_i * \text{Concentration}_i)}{100 * N} \quad (1)$$

where N represents the number of pore volume injection, cumulative fluid injection relates to treatment fluid which can be either single solution or mixture fluid injection, and its unit is cc, material price unit depends on the price of treatment materials and its unit is \$/cc, concentration percentages can be acid or salt solution as percentage “%”, finally, index i

denotes to used acids or solutions.

Figure 5 shows sandstone acidizing using traditional technique is more expansive rather than new treatment technique. Since the traditional treatment technique is used the hydrochloric acid for both pre-flush and post-flush stages, and the cost of hydrochloric acid is more expansive than ammonium chloride solution, and the cost of HCl is almost four times NH₄Cl solution cost. Consequently, the ammonium chloride solution in pre- and post-treatment stages is selected in order to be more economic benefit, and hydrochloric acid can produce from the chemical reactions between the solutions as explained in literature review. However, the cost of organic mud acids mixture “1.5\$/PV” is lower than inorganic mud acids mixture “2.1\$/PV”. Since the organic acid “acetic acid” can be found naturally, on the other hand, hydrochloric acid needs specific preparations to get it chemically. The obtained materials such as cleaning, additives, transport, washing and others are significant in treatment job, by the way, these are assumed to be forty percentage of cumulative cost of treatment stages. In the Figure 5, the total cost of traditional treatment technique with Tax included, which is corresponding with 8.6\$/PV, is obviously higher than new treatment technique cost which its value is 2.8\$/PV. Consequently, the implementation of new

treatment technique in undamaged sandstone core is more effective economically rather than traditional treatment technique, in addition, it is environmentally friendly.

To study more deeply about the treatments costs for damaged core, the Figure 6 is addressed the real study economically where is located in the field. It is indicated that the total cost of new treatment technique in damaged sandstone core is 3.0\$/PV, on the contrary, the total cost value for traditional treatment technique in damaged sandstone core is almost 9.2\$/PV. Hence, all results agree that the traditional treatment techniques are costly and useless comparing with the new treatment technique.

6. Conclusion and Recommendation

This paper is addressed to investigate a new technique that can be applied to stimulate and

treat sandstone reservoirs from any damages that can be occurred from drilling mud. In addition, it is also studied comparison between traditional and new treatments techniques economically. It is chemically proved that the hydrochloric acid can be produced by chemical reactions between fluids that have been used in this paper. The organic mud acids mixture, which is composed of 2wt% hydrofluoric acid and 15wt% acetic acid and mix them with 5wt% ammonium chloride solution, can be provided the successful treatment technique in both damaged and undamaged sandstone reservoirs. On the contrary, the treatment of fractured sandstone cannot lead to return permeability to original situation and value. Economically, the new treatment technique is concluded the efficient technique that can be utilized in the industry to save more money as well as time.

Figure 5: Costs of Traditional Treatment and New Treatment Techniques for Undamaged Sandstone Core “Core B”.

Figure 6: Costs of Traditional Treatment and New Treatment Techniques for Damaged Sandstone Core “Core A”.

More investigations about the treatment processes are experimentally recommended to apply in various sandstone reservoirs under reservoir conditions such as temperature and pressure. In addition, simulation studies of treatment in both fractured and unfractured sandstone reservoirs are recommended to study in order to create several scenarios without consuming materials and time.

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